

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: CANADA/US

Many hands on deck: Working with communities to monitor lake water quality

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As the global profile of citizen and community science continues to rise, so do opportunities available to limnologists and lake management professionals. For instance, in the United States alone, the National Water Quality Monitoring Council estimated in 2014 that there were 1,720 volunteer monitoring groups active across the country, collecting water quality data on a wide range of parameters including phosphorus, nitrogen, dissolved oxygen, pH, temperature, and conductivity (NWQMC; Albus *et al.*, 2019). While many target rivers and streams, a significant number of citizen science groups are engaged in sampling lakes.

The potential benefits that such groups can provide to limnology and lake management are well-known: they are capable of gathering information at spatial and temporal scales that would otherwise be difficult or costly to collect; the regularity of their efforts is crucial to obtaining essential baseline data; and they provide eyes on the ground to flag areas that are potentially in need of further study or management action. Nevertheless, many scientists and environmental managers still express concerns about data quality, and there is evidence to suggest that attitudes towards the presumed accuracy and reliability of volunteer-generated data act as a barrier to the use of these valuable datasets, even when programs have extensive mechanisms for volunteer training, protocols for quality assurance, and oversight by professionals (Albus *et al.*, 2019). In response to these concerns, a growing number of comparative studies have demonstrated that volunteers can produce scientifically-credible data on par with professionals, at least for many common indicators (Hoyer & Canfield, 2021).

Scientists tend to be most interested in citizen science as a way to increase the scale of data collection, but there are a host of other beneficial outcomes for environmental management, including improved community-based management, inter-organization communication, stakeholder literacy, attitude changes, empowerment, engagement, and improved social capital for participants (Stepenuck & Genskow, 2018). Turrini *et al.* (2018) identify a “threefold potential” of environmental citizen science, where projects can simultaneously advance objectives related to knowledge generation (creating new “opportunities to generate knowledge and insights which are new and relevant for science, society, or administration and management, especially with respect to nature conservation”); learning (improving environmental literacy and promoting increased public understanding of science); and civic participation (empowering citizens to become in-

involved in policy debates and decision-making processes). Other typologies of goals and outcomes of citizen science have made similar distinctions, differentiating between action-, conservation-, investigation-, and education- oriented programs (Wiggins & Crowston, 2011), or between project outcomes focused on increasing the volume of data, improving scientific and environmental literacy, building community leadership, fostering equitable collaborations between scientists and laypeople, producing locally-relevant environmental data that may be missing or inadequate, driving policy changes, or assisting with the enforcement of environmental laws and regulations (Kimura & Kinchy, 2016).

Success factors for citizen science-based water quality monitoring programs must take into account the attributes of volunteers (knowledge, experience, and awareness; socio-economic background; motivations), the attributes of institutions (support structures, organizational cultures), as well as the interactions between them (San Llorente Capdevila *et al.*, 2020). In 2015, the European Citizen Science Association published their “Ten Principles of Citizen Science” (ECSA, 2015) to codify best practices and guiding principles which can inform the successful development and management of volunteer-based programs and help to strike a balance between the scientific and social values of citizen science practice.

The authors are involved with three successful lake monitoring programs which are focused on obtaining high quality data, but which also have reported outcomes related to transformational volunteer experiences and citizen empowerment (Fig. 1). In Ontario, Canada, the Lake Partner Program (LPP) facilitates a network of around 600 independent volunteers who record Secchi disc depth and water temperature readings and collect water samples for laboratory analysis of phosphorus and calcium concentrations (Fig. 2). Established in 1996, the program is a partnership between the Federation of Ontario Cottagers' Associations and the Ministry of the Environment, Conservation, and Parks (MECP). In Connecticut, USA, volunteers in the Citizen-led Environmental Observatory (CLEO) record Secchi disc depth and other visual observations and collect water samples for nutrient and cyanobacterial toxin analysis (Fig. 3). Established in 2006, the project is a partnership between Friends of the Lake (Lillinonah) and Fairfield University. In New Hampshire, the state sponsored Volunteer Lake Assessment Program (VLAP) was launched in 1985 to establish a citizen-based lake sampling program to assist NHDES in evaluating lake water quality throughout the state, and to empower citizens with information about the health of the state's lakes and ponds. Local lake associations have partnered with NH Department of Environmental Services (DES) to enable this effort. One of the partners, the Lake Sunapee Protective Association (LSPA), runs a designated DES-satellite laboratory for the VLAP program, training, educating, and processing samples for 25 lakes and ponds in Central West New Hampshire.

“What do you value most about citizen science?”

Fig. 1 Themes discussed by LPP volunteers when asked what they value about participating in citizen science. Each pie slice shows the percentage of all comments that relate to each theme

Fig. 2 FOCA Director Terry Rees sampling for the LPP. See <https://foca.on.ca/lake-partner-program-overview/> for more information about the LPP.

Fig. 3 CLEO volunteer records data during the annual training program. See <https://tinyurl.com/CLEOLillionah> for more information about CLEO.

Even in programs that are focused explicitly on obtaining useful baseline data, we have seen volunteers report outcomes related to empowerment, community engagement, and transformational learning (Fig. 1). Volunteers use the baseline data to inform conservation efforts on local lakes, for instance by educating their neighbors about the importance of ongoing water quality monitoring, initiating community-run invasive species monitoring programs, or creating lake by-laws related to natural shorelines, mandatory septic inspections, or phosphate use. As one LPP volunteer expressed, “You can go armed with the information and if it’s backed up by an organization like the Lake Partner Program, I think you’re that much more credible. So, in that sense it is empowering. You’ve got the weight of this expertise behind any argument.” CLEO volunteers have expressed that they talk more with their neighbors after participating in the program, and that taking on this work gives them a sense of pride in the organization. Some have reported that having the data gives them a seat at the table with the state management agency, which they have used to argue for revised permits on the wastewater treatment plant. The experience has also contributed to some transformational life outcomes. One participant who started volunteering as a teen now works for a limnology consulting firm; another changed her major to environmental biology as a result of learning more about water quality issues as a volunteer.

Some distinguish between research-oriented citizen science and empowerment or justice-oriented community science (Cooper *et al.*, 2021). Yet regardless of the explicit goals of any given citizen science program, we have observed that education and empowerment outcomes can be present in citizen science programs that are focused primarily on obtaining good data. Thus, it is useful, practical, and important to carefully consider the sociological dimensions of the experience of volunteers in all types of citizen science. Doing so can make for better citizens and better science.

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